

BANK PRODUCTS AND THEIR IMPORTANCE

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Abstract: In the context of the development and active use of new digital technologies, the demand for banking services and products is increasing, attention is being paid to quality, and the amount of bank resources is in many ways directly proportional to the volume of banking services and products provided. As a result, it is shown that the volume of banking services and products provided is directly related to the amount of bank resources. This situation is explained by the fact that modern banks ensure an increase in income and profit.

Attention is drawn to the fact that providing banks with professional personnel, selecting them, and utilizing their abilities, as well as the effective use of world practice and modern new information technologies in analyzing data, are the main directions of universal banking development.

Key words: Banking services, banking products, universal banking, professional staff, funds, new digital technologies, financial resources, banking resources, commission income, credit services.

Introduction

Currently, banking institutions are focusing on the concept of credit as one of the means of attracting customers to offer a wide range of services. It is noted that the more a bank strives to provide its customers with not “one-time”, but complex and long-term services, the higher the level of commission income is guaranteed. Therefore, it is preferable to systematically implement an innovative integrated approach to working with customers, the essence of which is to form long-term cooperation and create an opportunity to work with the client as a business partner.

Our daily life cannot be imagined without plastic cards, because they have penetrated all spheres of human activity. This is manifested both in trade and in the provision of various services. One of such operations, which is in great demand today, is acquiring - a service that allows organizations to accept cards issued by banking institutions as payment for goods and services sold to customers. Organizations that use acquisitions gain competitive advantages by increasing turnover.

For banking institutions, the commission income from these operations is beneficial both in terms of increasing the number of new customers, who, in turn, are expected to offer new, more profitable services to commercial banks.

Review of relevant literature.

The essence and content of banking services or products have been methodologically and practically studied by domestic and foreign economists and the corresponding scientific conclusions and practical recommendations have been made.

In his scientific ideas and works, the economist Ternovsky emphasizes the following ideas about the essence of banking products, namely, that in modern scientific and practical literature in the field of economics and finance, the term “banking product” is understood as a service or a set of interrelated services designed to meet the needs of bank customers.

According to such scientists as Platonova and Higgins, a banking product is a separate banking service or a set of banking services offered to customers on standard terms. By this, they mean a set of loans, deposits, plastic cards, money transfers and other banking operations.

According to Khafizova's research, a banking product (service) is a set of various actions of banks in the financial market, monetary transactions carried out by them in accordance with the

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supply and demand for money, as well as monetary transactions carried out in accordance with the supply and demand for money, improving and increasing the efficiency of banking entrepreneurship.

Vagaitseva and Shmireva emphasize in their research that the development of new digital technologies and their active use affect the economic relations of credit institutions with clients in the field of the availability of products and services. At the same time, they emphasize that the activities of banks in creating and producing products for clients have risen to a new level due to the development of technologies and innovations in this area.

Economists Abaeva and Khasanov emphasize in their research that their idea is that banking products and services are related to financial resources, while the process of providing the main types of banking services is based on the use of cash or non-cash funds.

As a result of the analysis conducted on the topic, it became clear that we witnessed the following general characteristics of banking products and services: availability, contractual nature, complexity, service terms, use of cash or non-cash funds, development and active use of new digital technologies, connection with financial resources, and the inclusion of a set of loans, deposits, plastic cards, money transfers and other banking operations. Thus, in general, in the conditions of development and active use of new digital technologies, the demand for banking services and products increases, attention is paid to their quality, and the amount of bank resources is largely directly proportional to the volume of banking services and products provided. This situation ensures an increase in the income and profit of modern banks.

Research methodology.

In the process of researching this topic, the methods of logical thinking, scientific discussion and observation, systematic approach and comparison were widely used, based on the explanations and tariffs given by domestic and foreign economists in the field of bank services and the concepts of "banking products", "banking services", numerous theoretical literature related to the topic, empirical and practical research.

Analysis and discussion of results.

The promising direction of increasing commission income for the bank is also expanding and increasing the range of services provided through remote banking. These include Internet banking, which involves the provision of services based on the banking system of payments via the Internet, and services based on "mobile banking", which involves the provision of various banking products based on mobile technologies, which are currently gaining popularity.

The development of the bank's participation in the consumer credit segment is currently one of the most important factors in improving financial results in absolute and relative terms.

Therefore, as a direction for improving the financial performance of the bank, it is necessary to expand the range of credit products for consumer loans.

The credit products developed by the bank, on the one hand, reflect the specific features of capital turnover in various sectors of the real sector of the economy and the associated need to attract debt funds, on the other hand, they require maintaining their liquidity and ensuring the necessary level of profitability of the bank's capital and assets.

At the same time, the introduced or created credit products must meet the following criteria: minimal risk and maximum profitability. In case of successful implementation of the project, the bank will have the opportunity to attract additional clients, increase the efficiency of asset use, stabilize its financial position and increase competitiveness.

The classification of credit products is very diverse. They include the methods of issuance, currency and participants in credit relations, purpose, provision technology, collateral, term, payment methods, types of interest rates, methods of interest collection, categories of credit quality, objects and subjects of lending. In our opinion, all of them represent a set of banking and financial

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operations modified to meet the needs of any client, which can be placed as a new banking service or a combination of traditional banking services installed in a technological chain that allows solving the problem of a particular client and satisfying his demand for comprehensive services.

Simply put, a credit product is a program for interacting with a client, developed, created, invented or approved by a bank, on behalf of and at its expense, for the purpose of establishing relations with the client related to the placement of funds on terms of promptness, payment and repayment. In this case, the product should be distinguished from the lending service. The service belongs to the lending process itself. The product, as mentioned above, is a set of modified banking and financial operations designed to solve any need of the client, the use of which is regulated and strengthened on the basis of banking regulations.

The quantitative and qualitative development of credit products for individuals, striving to meet the needs of clients for credit resources to the maximum extent, allows the bank to increase its competitiveness. Based on this, the expansion of the types of consumer credit products should be named as the first direction of improving consumer credit in the bank.

The qualitative and quantitative development of the bank's credit products involves the implementation of work in the following areas:

- increasing the types of credit products;
- expanding the bases for using the types of credit products;
- simplifying and simplifying the technology of granting loans;
- developing pricing models for credit services;
- creating favorable conditions for organizing the sale of credit services;
- creating convenience for clients in the methods of loan repayment;
- ensuring attention to the qualifications and professional level of bank employees;
- expanding the branch network and providing it with modern technologies;

From the point of view of introducing new credit products, it is advisable to use the experience of other countries, taking into account the specifics of the Uzbek credit services market for the population. In particular, the most promising service for car loans is a loan program with the purchase of a car. The peculiarity of this program is that after a certain period of time specified in the terms of the loan agreement, the borrower can return the loaned car to the dealership, which will be required to pay the remaining debt to the bank. This is a buyback scheme, when after the payment period expires, the client returns the car to the dealership and buys a new car, and the old one serves as a down payment. Repurchase should not be confused with trade-in, because under the buyback program, the client signs a preliminary agreement that before the last payment he must sell the car to the dealership and pay off the debt, or sell the car himself and pay off the loan, or pay off your car loan in full and keep your car. The main disadvantage is that the final overpayment is significantly higher than usual, and the main advantage is the low monthly payments.

Another type of credit product in the car loan segment, which can be implemented differently, is the Tradein car loan.

This type of loan is suitable for clients who want to sell their car. In this case, the client takes a car on credit, and the old car serves as a down payment on a new loan. This scheme allows the client to solve several problems: buying a new car, getting rid of an old car, collecting a down payment. Another advantage of such a loan should be low interest rates, which should "exceed" the disadvantages of the lending scheme, which involves underestimating the value of an old car when evaluating it.

The development of sales of credit services to the population should be based on a study of the needs of the population. These needs can be assessed based on the results of social surveys that allow identifying the areas of greatest "consumer" interest among the population grouped

according to various criteria. The nature of the need for credit depends on the gender, age, and income level of an individual. For example, important decisions on the purchase of movable and immovable property are most often made by high-income men aged 21 to 45. The need for credit funds for home and household improvements (renovation, purchase of furniture and household appliances) is most often found in middle-aged women (aged 31 to 45) with low and middle incomes. Therefore, when forming standards for communicating with clients, banks should take into account the client's belonging to a certain group.

The analysis of the methods of informing clients about the credit services offered by commercial banks and systematizing them according to a number of criteria (the amount of resource and labor costs, the level of customer feedback) showed that e-mail and SMS messages are the most effective. Advertising plays an important and fundamental role in organizing the sale of credit services to the population. At the same time, the role of the Internet, especially in terms of social networks, is increasingly increasing.

Conclusions and suggestions

In conclusion, it should be said that the study of theoretical principles in the activities of commercial banks made it possible to identify the main distinctive features inherent in banking products and services. It also shows that some features of banking services are fundamentally different from banking products. Therefore, we see that the main elements of banking activities are close to each other, but we also see that they do not reflect a single essence.

In our opinion, as a result of the formation of universal banks in the modern banking system, it is expedient to perceive banking services as a set of economic relations of certain actions to provide certain banking products to clients. Banking products are manifested as the result of providing services to meet the needs of these clients.

The creation of new banking products by commercial banks is a necessary feature or aspect of the activities of commercial banks. As a result, it will serve to activate and renew the activities of banks in the banking market, increase the level of competitiveness, expand the number of clients and the service base, and increase profitability indicators. This, in turn, will have a direct positive impact on the main condition of market relations, which is the increase in bank income and increase in net profit.

Providing commercial banks with professional personnel, selecting and using their abilities, and effectively using world practice and modern new information technologies in analyzing data is the main direction of universal banking development. In such conditions, as a final result, we create wide-ranging opportunities for creating new banking products and implementing them in practice.

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